

Distance functions of carabids in crop fields depend on functional traits, crop type and adjacent habitat: a synthesis

ESM 2: Modeling workflow

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Summary

This appendix describes the Bayesian modeling workflow used in our study, which follows the principles outlined in Gabry et al. (2019). It includes all the code required to reproduce the models reported in our paper. This appendix is organized in a three-level nested fashion: first by workflow step, then by response variable (species richness, activity density), and then by specific model (i.e. a full dataset model and separate models based on dietary subsets or body size subsets).

We begin with the specification of priors, which is an iterative process (reported in abbreviated form for the sake of clarity) in which candidate prior sets are evaluated via prior predictive checks to ensure that the parameter space considered by the model predicts broadly realistic data *before* seeing the empirical data (Wesner and Pomeranz 2021). The use of regularizing (as opposed to flat or weakly informative) priors is especially important when using log-link generalized models, since the right tail of the parameter distribution can translate into implausibly high data predictions on the response scale (Gabry et al. 2019).

Having chosen principled priors, we then fit the models to empirical data using the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) algorithm of Stan (Stan Development Team 2021), accessed via the R package `brms` (Bürkner 2017). We then verify the integrity of the HMC process by checking that sampling chains have converged ($R_{\text{hat}} \sim 1$), that effective sample sizes (ESS) are adequate, and that divergent transitions have been avoided.

When the computation integrity of a model has been confirmed, we evaluate its empirical realism by performing posterior predictive checks in which the distribution of data simulated from the posterior of the model is compared to the distribution of the data used to fit it. If there are no systematic discrepancies between the simulated and empirical data, the model can be considered a plausible representation of the real-world data generating process that is the subject of inference, justifying the ecological interpretation of parameter estimations.

All data processing, modeling, and visualization were done in R (R Core Team 2021). Data handling was done with the `tidyverse` suite of packages (Wickham et al. 2019). Visualizations appearing in the main text of the manuscript were produced with the R packages `ggplot2` (Wickham 2016), `tidybayes` (Kay 2020), and `ggdist` (Kay 2021).

Prepare environment

```
# Attach packages
library(brms) # a Stan front-end for Bayesian modeling
library(tidyverse) # data handling

# Optimize setting for Stan
rstan::rstan_options(auto_write = TRUE)
options(mc.cores = parallel::detectCores())

# Load data
meta_rich <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich.rds")
meta_rich_predatory <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_predatory2.rds")
meta_rich_granivorous <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_granivorous.rds")
meta_rich_omnivorous <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_omnivorous2.rds")
meta_rich_omnivorous_b <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_omnivorous3.rds")
meta_abund <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund.rds")
meta_abund_diet <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_diet2.rds")
meta_abund_diet_b <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_diet3.rds")
meta_abund_size <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_size.rds")
meta_CWM <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_CWM2.rds")
```

Specify priors

In this section, we visualize the priors for each model and describe the reasoning behind our choices. Note that, in addition to the slope, intercept, and standard deviation parameters described below, our models also include correlation priors for varying effects (site nested in study), for which we use the weakly regularizing LKG distribution [lkg(1)] that `brms` (Bürkner 2017) uses as a default. Our gamma models (activity density) also include a shape parameter governing the gamma distribution. For this, which has no intuitive biological meaning, we replace the default flat prior with a very broad but proper $N(0, 2.5)$, since prior predictive simulation is only possible when all parameters have a proper (i.e. non-flat) prior.

Richness

Global slope

Distance The transformed slope coefficient is the factor by which species richness changes with every 100 m of distance from the field edge. Could it double every 10 m? Maybe. Could it even quadruple? That seems unlikely, but we won't rule it out completely. We will aim for a prior that gets very skinny above 4 on the response scale. The left tail of our prior should allow values very close to zero (though zero itself is not possible, since an exponentiated distribution is zero-bounded). $N(0, 0.75)$ seems reasonable.

```
slope_prior_richness <-
  # a range of parameter values imagined on the link scale
  tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 3, 0.01)) %>%
  # exponentiated parameter values, now interpreted as multiplier per unit x
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),
  # get probability densities
         N.0_075 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 0.75)) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),
               names_to = "prior",
               values_to = "density")

# Plot
```

```
ggplot(slope_prior_richness, aes(x_response, density)) +
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +
  xlim(c(0, 10)) +
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +
  theme_light() +
  ggtitle("Richness ~ distance global prior (response scale)")
```


Trap-days The conditional effect of `log.trap.days` should always be positive. Perhaps we don't want to make it strictly zero-bounded, but we at least want the prior informatively centered above zero. On the response scale, that means above 1. It's about $1 \times \log(\text{trap.days})$ when you go from 14 trapping days to 40 trapping days. It's roughly another $1 \times \log(\text{trap.day})$ to go from 40 to 100. By what factor could we expect richness to increase over those intervals? A factor of 4 seems a reasonable upper extreme. $N(0.5, 0.4)$ would be a reasonable prior.

```
slope_prior_richness2 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 3, 0.01)) %>%
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),
         N.05_04 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0.5, sd = 0.4)) %>%

  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),
               names_to = "prior",
               values_to = "density")

# Plot
ggplot(slope_prior_richness2, aes(x_response, density)) +
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +
  xlim(c(0, 6)) +
```

```
labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +
theme_light() +
ggtitle("Richness ~ trapping days prior (response scale)")
```


Group-level slopes

Each group-level slope parameter gets added (on the link scale) to the global slope parameter to get the slope for each group. So, these priors reflect how much each group can deviate from the reference level (crop = cereal, habitat = control). A prior of $N(0, 0.75)$ gets skinny around ± 2 . Let's imagine a neutral global slope parameter of 0 on the link scale. A group-level parameter of 2 would mean a group-level slope of a 22% increase per 10 m. That's pretty dramatic. A group-level parameter of -2 would mean a slope of -18% per 10 m. That is also very steep. But perhaps differences of this magnitude are not impossible. We'll see how a prior of $N(0, 0.75)$ performs in prior predictive checks.

```
slope_prior_richness3 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 3, 0.01)) %>%
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),
         N.0_075 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 0.75)) %>%

  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),
              names_to = "prior",
              values_to = "density")

# Plot
ggplot(slope_prior_richness3, aes(x_link, density)) +
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +
  #xlim(c(0, 6)) +
```

```
labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +
theme_light() +
ggtitle("Richness ~ distance group-level prior (link scale)")
```


Global intercept

For the global intercept term (Intercept), we are setting a prior on the value of species richness when all variables are at their means or reference levels. In a log link model, setting a normal prior on the link scale will result in a strictly positive prior on the response scale, which works well for the log-link models we are fitting. We should set it off a bit from zero, though, since we do not want to favor extremely low species counts. It looks like $N(2, 0.75)$ would be a very reasonable prior.

```
intercept_prior_richness1 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-5, 8, 0.01)) %>%
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),
         N.02_075 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 2, sd = 0.75)) %>%

  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),
               names_to = "prior",
               values_to = "density")

# Plot
ggplot(intercept_prior_richness1, aes(x_response, density)) +
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +
  xlim(c(0, 80)) +
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +
  theme_light() +
```

```
ggtitle("Richness global intercept prior (response scale)")
```


Group-level intercepts

As for the group-level slope parameters, the group-level intercept parameters are added to the global parameter on the link scale. If we take a global intercept value from the fat part of the prior—let's say 2.5 on the link scale, ~12 species on the response scale—a group-level intercept parameter of 2 would mean 90 species. And -2 would mean < 2 species. This is tricky, because you can see how this will tend to explode on the upper end. But we don't want to constrain it too much on the lower end, since it's possible that a given group could have very low species richness. I think $N(0, 0.75)$ is a reasonable start, but again we'll have to see how the prior predictive check goes.

```
intercept_prior_richness2 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-5, 8, 0.01)) %>%  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         N.0_075 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 0.75)) %>%  
  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(intercept_prior_richness2, aes(x_link, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  xlim(c(-3, 3)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +
```

```
ggtitle("Richness group-level intercept prior (link scale)")
```


SD for study/site varying effect

These priors define the normal distribution, centered on the grand mean, from which the deviation of study and site are estimated. Because the distribution is centered on the mean, the model is skeptical of large deviations in studies/sites, as long as the sd prior is tight enough. We'll go with $N(0, 1)$ as a reasonable starting place.

```
sd_prior_richness1 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-5, 8, 0.01)) %>%  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         N.0_1 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 1)) %>%  
  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(sd_prior_richness1, aes(x_response, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  xlim(c(0, 20)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +  
  ggtitle("Richness sd prior (response scale)")
```

Richness sd prior (response scale)

Activity density

Global slope

As for richness, the task here is to choose a prior that allows realistic values for the factor by which activity density could increase per 100 m (since it is the upper bound, not the lower bound, that could destabilize the model). $N(0, 0.75)$ seems a good place to start.

```
slope_prior_ad <-  
  # a range of parameter values imagined on the link scale  
  tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 3, 0.01)) %>%  
  # exponentiated parameter values, now interpreted as multiplier per unit x  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         # get probability densities  
         N_0_075 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 0.75)) %>%  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(slope_prior_ad, aes(x_response, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  xlim(c(0, 10)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +  
  ggtitle("Activity density ~ distance global prior (response scale)")
```

Activity density ~ distance global prior (response scale)

Group-level slopes

For the group level terms, we are again setting a prior on the factor by which each group will differ from the global intercept. As in the richness model, we will use $N(0, 0.75)$.

```
slope_prior_ad2 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 3, 0.01)) %>%  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         N.0_05 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 0.5)) %>%  
  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(slope_prior_ad2, aes(x_link, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  #xlim(c(0, 6)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +  
  ggtitle("Activity density ~ distance group-level prior (link scale)")
```

Activity density ~ distance group-level prior (link scale)

Global intercept

For the global intercept term, we are setting a prior on the value of individuals caught per trapping day when all variables are at their means or reference levels. $N(1,1)$ seems reasonable.

```
intercept_prior_ad <-  
  # a range of parameter values imagined on the link scale  
  tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 5, 0.01)) %>%  
  # exponentiated parameter values, now interpreted as multiplier per unit x  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         # get probability densities  
         N.1_1 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 1, sd = 1)) %>%  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(intercept_prior_ad, aes(x_response, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  xlim(c(0, 50)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +  
  ggtitle("Activity global intercept prior (response scale)")
```

Activity global intercept prior (response scale)

Group-level intercept

For activity density, we will use a somewhat tighter $N(0, 0.5)$ prior for group-level intercepts, since this model tends to explode into very high predictions in the prior predictive check.

```
intercept_prior_ad2 <-  
  # a range of parameter values imagined on the link scale  
  tibble(x_link = seq(-3, 5, 0.01)) %>%  
  # exponentiated parameter values, now interpreted as multiplier per unit x  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         # get probability densities  
         N_0_05 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 0.5)) %>%  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(intercept_prior_ad2, aes(x_link, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  #xlim(c(0, 10)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +  
  ggtitle("Activity density group-level intercept prior (link scale)")
```

Activity density group-level intercept prior (link scale)

SD for study/site varying effect

For the standard deviation prior, we will again use $N(0,1)$.

```
sd_prior_ad1 <- tibble(x_link = seq(-5, 8, 0.01)) %>%  
  mutate(x_response = exp(x_link),  
         N.0_1 = dnorm(x_link, mean = 0, sd = 1)) %>%  
  
  pivot_longer(cols = c(-x_link, -x_response),  
              names_to = "prior",  
              values_to = "density")  
  
# Plot  
ggplot(sd_prior_ad1, aes(x_response, density)) +  
  geom_area(alpha = 0.5) +  
  xlim(c(0, 20)) +  
  labs(x = "Coefficient", y = "Probability density") +  
  theme_light() +  
  ggtitle("Activity density sd prior (response scale)")
```

Activity density sd prior (response scale)

Call prior sets

Richness

```
priors_rich00 <- c(prior(normal(0, 0.75),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = distance100),  
                  prior(normal(0.5, 0.4),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = log.trap.days),  
                  prior(normal(0, 0.75),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = `distance100:crop.poolOilseed`),  
                  prior(normal(0, 0.75),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = `distance100:crop.poolVegetable`),  
                  prior(normal(0, 0.75),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = `distance100:crop.poolMaize`),  
                  prior(normal(0, 0.75),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = `distance100:crop.poolLegume`),  
                  prior(normal(0, 0.75),  
                    class = b,  
                    coef = `distance100:snh.typeherbaceous`),
```

```

prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:snh.typewoody`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolLegume`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolMaize`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolOilseed`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolVegetable`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `snh.typeherbaceous`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `snh.typewoody`),
prior(normal(2, 0.75),
      class = Intercept),
prior(normal(0, 1),
      class = sd)
)

```

Activity density

```

priors_abund00 <- c(prior(normal(0, 0.75),
                        class = b,
                        coef = distance100),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:crop.poolOilseed`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:crop.poolVegetable`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:crop.poolMaize`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:crop.poolLegume`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:snh.typeherbaceous`),
prior(normal(0, 0.75),
      class = b,
      coef = `distance100:snh.typewoody`),
prior(normal(0, 0.5),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolLegume`),

```

```

prior(normal(0, 0.5),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolMaize`),
prior(normal(0, 0.5),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolOilseed`),
prior(normal(0, 0.5),
      class = b,
      coef = `crop.poolVegetable`),
prior(normal(0, 0.5),
      class = b,
      coef = `snh.typeherbaceous`),
prior(normal(0, 0.5),
      class = b,
      coef = `snh.typewoody`),
prior(normal(1, 1),
      class = Intercept),
prior(normal(0, 2.5),
      class = shape),
prior(normal(0, 1),
      class = sd)
)

```

Run prior predictive checks

In a prior-predictive check, a model is run (i.e. sampled via HMC) using only its priors (i.e. its “joint prior,” then high-dimensional space defined by its full prior set). This produces a posterior distribution just like running the model with data, but the posterior expresses only the information built into the model via its structure and its priors. It hasn’t “learned” from the new empirical data yet. When we visualize the posterior distribution that results from sampling the joint prior, we should see that the bulk of the probability mass occupies plausible values. In this case, we will use a set of histograms that depicts 10 iterations of sampling from posterior along with the distribution of the empirical data that our model has not yet seen. Ideally, the distribution of values drawn from the posterior should be considerably broader than the distribution of the empirical data, but not so much broader than the model places a lot of probability density on regions parameter space that generate data that are implausible (e.g. there will never be 40,000 species of carabids at any distance from a field edge).

Richness

Total

This configuration still predicts huge values of richness sometimes, but it concentrates the probability density between 0 and 100 species, which is where we want it to be.

```

brm_rich_00_pp <- brm(richness ~
  distance100 +
  log.trap.days +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = poisson(link = "log"),
  prior = priors_rich00,
)

```

```

iter = 2000,
chains = 4,
sample_prior = "only",
data = meta_rich)

```

```

pp_check(brm_rich_00_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 40) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 100))

```


Predatory

```

brm_rich_11_pp <- brm(richness ~
  distance100 +
  log.trap.days +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
family = poisson(link = "log"),
prior = priors_rich00,
iter = 2000,
chains = 4,
sample_prior = "only",
data = meta_rich_predatory)

```

```
## Compiling Stan program...
```

```
## recompiling to avoid crashing R session
```

```
## Start sampling
```

```
pp_check(brm_rich_11_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 40) +  
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 100))
```

```
## Using 10 posterior draws for ppc type 'hist' by default.
```


Omnivorous

```
brm_rich_12_pp <- brm(richness ~  
  distance100 +  
  log.trap.days +  
  snh.type +  
  crop.pool +  
  distance100:snh.type +  
  distance100:crop.pool +  
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),  
  family = poisson(link = "log"),  
  prior = priors_rich00,  
  iter = 2000,  
  chains = 4,  
  sample_prior = "only",  
  data = meta_rich_omnivorous)
```

```
## Compiling Stan program...
```

```
## recompiling to avoid crashing R session
```

```
## Start sampling
```

```
pp_check(brm_rich_12_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 40) +  
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 100))
```

```
## Using 10 posterior draws for ppc type 'hist' by default.
```


Omnivorous only (without *Poecilus cupreus*)

```
brm_rich_12b_pp <- brm(richness ~  
  distance100 +  
  log.trap.days +  
  snh.type +  
  crop.pool +  
  distance100:snh.type +  
  distance100:crop.pool +  
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),  
  family = poisson(link = "log"),  
  prior = priors_rich00,  
  iter = 2000,  
  chains = 4,  
  sample_prior = "only",  
  data = meta_rich_omnivorous_b)
```

```
## Compiling Stan program...
```

```
## recompiling to avoid crashing R session
```

```
## Start sampling
```

```
pp_check(brm_rich_12b_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 40) +  
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 100))
```

```
## Using 10 posterior draws for ppc type 'hist' by default.
```


Granivorous

```
brm_rich_20_pp <- brm(richness ~  
  distance100 +  
  log.trap.days +  
  snh.type +  
  crop.pool +  
  distance100:snh.type +  
  distance100:crop.pool +  
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),  
  family = poisson(link = "log"),  
  prior = priors_rich00,  
  iter = 2000,  
  chains = 4,  
  sample_prior = "only",  
  data = meta_rich_granivorous)
```

```
pp_check(brm_rich_20_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 40) +
```

```
coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 100))
```


Activity density (total)

Total

```
brm_abund_00_pp <- brm(abund.std ~  
  distance100 +  
  snh.type +  
  crop.pool +  
  distance100:snh.type +  
  distance100:crop.pool +  
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),  
  family = "hurdle_gamma",  
  prior = priors_abund00,  
  iter = 2000,  
  chains = 4,  
  sample_prior = "only",  
  data = meta_abund)  
  
pp_check(brm_abund_00_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 5) +  
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 20))
```


Predatory

```
brm_abund_11_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_diet, diet == "predatory"))
```

```
## Compiling Stan program...
```

```
## recompiling to avoid crashing R session
```

```
## Start sampling
```

```
pp_check(brm_abund_11_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```

```
## Using 10 posterior draws for ppc type 'hist' by default.
```


Omnivorous only

```
brm_abund_12_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_diet, diet == "omnivorous"))
```

```
## Compiling Stan program...
```

```
## recompiling to avoid crashing R session
```

```
## Start sampling
```

```
pp_check(brm_abund_12_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```

```
## Using 10 posterior draws for ppc type 'hist' by default.
```


Omnivorous only (without *Poecilus cupreus*)

```
brm_abund_12b_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_diet_b, diet == "omnivorous"))
```

```
## Compiling Stan program...
```

```
## recompiling to avoid crashing R session
```

```
## Start sampling
```

```
pp_check(brm_abund_12b_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```

```
## Using 10 posterior draws for ppc type 'hist' by default.
```


Granivorous

```
brm_abund_20_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  control = list(adapt_delta = 0.9), # trying to avoid a few DTs
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_diet, diet == "granivorous"))

pp_check(brm_abund_20_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```


Small

```
brm_abund_30_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_size, size.class == "small"))

pp_check(brm_abund_30_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```


Medium

```
brm_abund_40_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_size, size.class == "medium"))

pp_check(brm_abund_40_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```


Large

```
brm_abund_50_pp <- brm(abund.std ~
  distance100 +
  snh.type +
  crop.pool +
  distance100:snh.type +
  distance100:crop.pool +
  (1 + distance100 | study/site),
  family = "hurdle_gamma",
  prior = priors_abund00,
  iter = 2000,
  chains = 4,
  sample_prior = "only",
  data = filter(meta_abund_size, size.class == "large"))

pp_check(brm_abund_50_pp, type = "hist", binwidth = 10) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 40))
```


Update models with data

In this step, we simply add the data to the models already specified in our prior-predictive checks. Now, the resulting posterior will be informed by both the priors and the data. This process can take a long time, so we will load these previously sampled models from saved files.

Richness

Total

```
brm_rich_00 <- update(brm_rich_00_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,
  file = "../output/brm_rich_00")
```

Predatory

```
brm_rich_11 <- update(brm_rich_11_pp,
  sample_prior = TRUE,
  iter = 4000,
  file = "../output/brm_rich_11") # local
```

The desired updates require recompiling the model

Omnivorous

```
brm_rich_12 <- update(brm_rich_12_pp,  
  sample_prior = TRUE,  
  iter = 4000,  
  file = "../output/brm_rich_12")
```

The desired updates require recompiling the model

Omnivorous (without *Poecilus cupreus*)

```
brm_rich_12b <- update(brm_rich_12b_pp,  
  sample_prior = TRUE,  
  iter = 4000,  
  file = "../output/brm_rich_12b")
```

The desired updates require recompiling the model

Granivorous

```
brm_rich_20 <- update(brm_rich_20_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,  
  file = "../output/brm_rich_20")
```

Activity density

Total

```
brm_abund_00 <- update(brm_abund_00_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,  
  file = "../output/brm_abund_00")
```

Predatory

```
brm_abund_11 <- update(brm_abund_11_pp,  
  sample_prior = TRUE,  
  iter = 4000,  
  file = "../output/brm_abund_11")
```

The desired updates require recompiling the model

Omnivorous

```
brm_abund_12 <- update(brm_abund_12_pp,  
  sample_prior = TRUE,  
  iter = 4000,  
  file = "../output/brm_abund_12")
```

The desired updates require recompiling the model

Omnivorous (without *Poecilus cupreus*)

```
brm_abund_12b <- update(brm_abund_12b_pp,  
  sample_prior = TRUE,  
  iter = 4000,  
  file = "../output/brm_abund_12b")
```

```
## The desired updates require recompiling the model
```

Granivorous

```
brm_abund_20 <- update(brm_abund_20_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,  
                      file = "../output/brm_abund_20")
```

Small

```
brm_abund_30 <- update(brm_abund_30_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,  
                      file = "../output/brm_abund_30")
```

Medium

```
brm_abund_40 <- update(brm_abund_40_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,  
                      iter = 5000,  
                      file = "../output/brm_abund_40")
```

Large

```
brm_abund_50 <- update(brm_abund_50_pp, sample_prior = TRUE,  
                      iter = 5000,  
                      file = "../output/brm_abund_50")
```

Evaluate computational integrity

The `brms` package (Bürkner 2017) prints informative model summaries when a model object is called. What we are interested in here is the evaluation of the HMC algorithm found in the last three columns of each table. The Rhat value indicates whether sampling chains converged on a coherent posterior as opposed, for example, to getting stuck in different local optima. An Rhat very close to 1 means that chains converged successfully. Bulk- and tail-ESS describe the effective sample size associated with each parameter, which is a metric that corrects the absolute number of samples drawn by the HMC process for the degree of autocorrelation between samples. When ESS is too low, parameter estimates cannot be considered reliable. This triggers a warning printed at the bottom of the output when a model object is called. Finally, divergent transitions are iterations of the sampling process that “break” the underlying logic of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo, typically due to very narrow geometry in the posterior that cannot be navigated effectively given the step size of the HMC algorithm. To the extent that divergent transitions occur during the sampling process, the HMC devolves to a mere random walk, and the posterior is not sampled informatively. Ideally, there should be no divergent transitions at all. Any divergent transitions will trigger a warning message at the bottom of the output when a model object is called.

Richness

Total

```
brm_rich_00
```

```
## Family: poisson  
## Links: mu = log  
## Formula: richness ~ distance100 + log.trap.days + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + dist  
## Data: meta_rich (Number of observations: 2768)
```

```

## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
## Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 0.54 0.08 0.40 0.73 1.00 2308
## sd(distance100) 0.17 0.07 0.05 0.33 1.00 3810
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.41 0.39 -0.45 0.96 1.00 4948
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 3803
## sd(distance100) 4010
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 3116
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
## Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 0.24 0.01 0.22 0.27 1.00 2681
## sd(distance100) 0.05 0.04 0.00 0.13 1.00 2692
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.30 0.52 -0.97 0.87 1.00 6269
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 4595
## sd(distance100) 3482
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 5865
##
## Population-Level Effects:
## Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept 0.56 0.27 0.04 1.10 1.00
## distance100 -0.28 0.13 -0.54 -0.02 1.00
## log.trap.days 0.47 0.07 0.32 0.61 1.00
## snh.typewoody -0.08 0.05 -0.18 0.01 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous -0.05 0.04 -0.13 0.03 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable -0.01 0.10 -0.20 0.17 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed 0.23 0.04 0.15 0.30 1.00
## crop.poolLegume -0.08 0.07 -0.21 0.05 1.00
## crop.poolMaize -0.16 0.06 -0.29 -0.04 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody -0.12 0.16 -0.45 0.20 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.02 0.13 -0.28 0.24 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.44 0.33 -1.09 0.22 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed -0.05 0.12 -0.28 0.17 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.14 0.23 -0.32 0.59 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize -0.67 0.29 -1.23 -0.09 1.00
## Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept 1809 3126
## distance100 5464 6063
## log.trap.days 2483 3853
## snh.typewoody 5507 5613
## snh.typeherbaceous 5109 5681
## crop.poolVegetable 7541 5619
## crop.poolOilseed 6375 5837
## crop.poolLegume 7320 6144
## crop.poolMaize 8010 6419
## distance100:snh.typewoody 6297 5228
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 6042 5532
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 11898 6261

```

```

## distance100:crop.poolOilseed      7104      5970
## distance100:crop.poolLegume      8767      6686
## distance100:crop.poolMaize       9322      6098
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Predatory

```
brm_rich_11
```

```

## Family: poisson
## Links: mu = log
## Formula: richness ~ distance100 + log.trap.days + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + dist
## Data: meta_rich_predatory (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.60      0.10      0.44      0.82 1.00      1365
## sd(distance100)    0.12      0.08      0.01      0.30 1.00      2152
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.35      0.47     -0.73      0.97 1.00      6061
##
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      2508
## sd(distance100)    3136
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 5327
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.21      0.02      0.18      0.24 1.00      2695
## sd(distance100)    0.04      0.03      0.00      0.13 1.00      2931
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.04      0.56     -0.94      0.94 1.00      5656
##
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      4689
## sd(distance100)    3805
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 4902
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept          0.43      0.30     -0.14      1.03 1.00
## distance100        -0.09      0.16     -0.40      0.21 1.00
## log.trap.days      0.38      0.08      0.22      0.54 1.00
## snh.typewoody     -0.00      0.05     -0.11      0.10 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous -0.01      0.04     -0.09      0.07 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable -0.05      0.10     -0.25      0.15 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed   0.06      0.04     -0.02      0.14 1.00
## crop.poolLegume    -0.24      0.08     -0.40     -0.09 1.00
## crop.poolMaize     -0.22      0.07     -0.36     -0.09 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody -0.29      0.19     -0.66      0.07 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.12      0.16     -0.43      0.19 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.16      0.38     -0.90      0.60 1.00

```

```

## distance100:crop.poolOilseed      -0.13    0.13   -0.38    0.13  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume       0.18    0.27   -0.36    0.71  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize       -0.96    0.33   -1.58   -0.31  1.00
##                               Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept                        1373    2828
## distance100                       3366    4826
## log.trap.days                      1857    3409
## snh.typewoody                      4105    5520
## snh.typeherbaceous                 3768    5314
## crop.poolVegetable                 5149    5643
## crop.poolOilseed                   4567    5878
## crop.poolLegume                    5402    5656
## crop.poolMaize                     5679    5622
## distance100:snh.typewoody          3491    5119
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous     3548    4476
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable     8267    6138
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed       4534    6112
## distance100:crop.poolLegume        5968    6383
## distance100:crop.poolMaize         7120    6289
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Omnivorous

```
brm_rich_12
```

```

## Family: poisson
## Links: mu = log
## Formula: richness ~ distance100 + log.trap.days + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + dist
## Data: meta_rich_omnivorous (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          0.83    0.15    0.57    1.18  1.00    1726
## sd(distance100)         0.26    0.20    0.01    0.74  1.00    2971
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.18    0.59   -0.98    0.91  1.00    4377
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          2677
## sd(distance100)         4499
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 5105
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          0.03    0.02    0.00    0.08  1.00    4857
## sd(distance100)         0.06    0.05    0.00    0.19  1.00    5389
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.16    0.57   -0.97    0.92  1.00    8148
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          3893
## sd(distance100)         3986

```

```

## cor(Intercept,distance100)      5156
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept          -2.01     0.49   -2.94   -1.02  1.00
## distance100         0.41     0.32   -0.23    1.02  1.00
## log.trap.days       0.48     0.13    0.21    0.73  1.00
## snh.typewoody      -0.05     0.11   -0.27    0.16  1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous  0.00     0.09   -0.18    0.18  1.00
## crop.poolVegetable -0.66     0.37   -1.41    0.03  1.00
## crop.poolOilseed   0.21     0.09    0.03    0.39  1.00
## crop.poolLegume    0.20     0.14   -0.08    0.47  1.00
## crop.poolMaize     -0.09     0.14   -0.39    0.19  1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody 0.00     0.36   -0.70    0.71  1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.25     0.33   -0.89    0.43  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.26     0.69   -1.63    1.09  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed -0.28     0.28   -0.83    0.25  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume -0.21     0.44   -1.10    0.65  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 0.81     0.56   -0.27    1.91  1.00
##
##           Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept          1713    3330
## distance100        3586    5289
## log.trap.days      2174    3973
## snh.typewoody      6746    6407
## snh.typeherbaceous 5827    6101
## crop.poolVegetable 5761    5061
## crop.poolOilseed   7633    6029
## crop.poolLegume    7403    6290
## crop.poolMaize     7794    5714
## distance100:snh.typewoody 4882    5530
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 3506    4666
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 12524    5792
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 7691    6318
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 8044    5835
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 8350    6379
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Omnivorous (without *Poecilus cupreus*)

```
brm_rich_12b
```

```

## Family: poisson
## Links: mu = log
## Formula: richness ~ distance100 + log.trap.days + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + dist
## Data: meta_rich_omnivorous_b (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS

```

```

## sd(Intercept)          1.06    0.30    0.61    1.79 1.00    1978
## sd(distance100)        0.36    0.30    0.01    1.12 1.00    4686
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.06    0.58   -0.94    0.96 1.00    9427
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          3520
## sd(distance100)        4317
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 5125
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##                               Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          0.30    0.16    0.02    0.62 1.00    1356
## sd(distance100)        0.34    0.25    0.01    0.94 1.00    3689
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.03    0.58   -0.95    0.95 1.00    7440
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          2095
## sd(distance100)        3623
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 5306
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##                               Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept                -6.14    0.80   -7.63   -4.44 1.00
## distance100                -0.26    0.47   -1.19    0.64 1.00
## log.trap.days              1.06    0.20    0.64    1.44 1.00
## snh.typewoody              0.02    0.32   -0.61    0.63 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous        -0.02    0.24   -0.47    0.46 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable         0.28    0.54   -0.81    1.31 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed           0.23    0.30   -0.37    0.82 1.00
## crop.poolLegume            0.12    0.40   -0.67    0.87 1.00
## crop.poolMaize             1.29    0.35    0.60    1.98 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody  0.13    0.59   -1.04    1.30 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.10    0.49   -1.04    0.85 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.20    0.72   -1.59    1.20 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed -0.71    0.57   -1.81    0.39 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume -0.21    0.69   -1.57    1.15 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize  0.39    0.70   -1.01    1.81 1.00
##                               Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept                3191    3561
## distance100                7780    6123
## log.trap.days              3987    4629
## snh.typewoody              8660    6296
## snh.typeherbaceous         9176    6166
## crop.poolVegetable         6780    5810
## crop.poolOilseed           9179    6351
## crop.poolLegume            11418   6483
## crop.poolMaize             12683   6444
## distance100:snh.typewoody  11450   6172
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 7802    6254
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 17698   5623
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 13625   6407
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 15300   5834
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 15543   6308
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential

```

```
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).
```

Granivorous

```
brm_rich_20
```

```
## Family: poisson
## Links: mu = log
## Formula: richness ~ distance100 + log.trap.days + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + dist
## Data: meta_rich_granivorous (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 2000; warmup = 1000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 4000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 0.52 0.09 0.37 0.72 1.00 1025
## sd(distance100) 0.71 0.20 0.37 1.15 1.00 1370
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.19 0.30 -0.41 0.73 1.00 1052
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 1883
## sd(distance100) 2143
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 1755
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 0.30 0.03 0.24 0.35 1.00 1001
## sd(distance100) 0.12 0.08 0.01 0.28 1.01 927
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.34 0.48 -0.77 0.98 1.00 2015
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 1633
## sd(distance100) 1448
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 2421
##
## Population-Level Effects:
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept -1.52 0.34 -2.18 -0.84 1.01
## distance100 -0.87 0.27 -1.39 -0.33 1.00
## log.trap.days 0.67 0.09 0.49 0.84 1.01
## snh.typewoody -0.23 0.08 -0.39 -0.07 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous -0.10 0.06 -0.23 0.02 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable 0.10 0.17 -0.24 0.43 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed 0.62 0.06 0.50 0.74 1.00
## crop.poolLegume 0.14 0.11 -0.07 0.34 1.00
## crop.poolMaize -0.02 0.12 -0.25 0.21 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody -0.04 0.33 -0.69 0.60 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.03 0.25 -0.53 0.45 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.43 0.56 -1.50 0.65 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 0.41 0.23 -0.02 0.85 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.38 0.36 -0.33 1.10 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize -0.52 0.54 -1.59 0.55 1.00
## Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept 695 1204
## distance100 1621 2131
```

```

## log.trap.days           841      1506
## snh.typewoody          2711      2961
## snh.typeherbaceous     2040      2641
## crop.poolVegetable     2669      2690
## crop.poolOilseed       2194      2933
## crop.poolLegume        3047      3294
## crop.poolMaize         3631      3292
## distance100:snh.typewoody 2528      2812
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 1755      2176
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 3837      2740
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 2514      2981
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 3025      3538
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 4253      3387
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Activity density

Total

```
brm_abund_00
```

```

## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.pool
## Data: meta_abund (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 2000; warmup = 1000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 4000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##
## Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          1.05      0.15      0.80      1.40 1.00      1433
## sd(distance100)         0.30      0.14      0.03      0.58 1.00      1112
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.17      0.37     -0.65      0.81 1.00      3802
##
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          2263
## sd(distance100)         1134
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 1906
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##
## Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          0.75      0.02      0.70      0.79 1.00      1505
## sd(distance100)         0.10      0.08      0.00      0.28 1.00      1156
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.29      0.49     -0.96      0.82 1.00      4873
##
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          2105
## sd(distance100)         1375
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 2750
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##
## Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat

```

```

## Intercept                0.61      0.22      0.17      1.03 1.01
## distance100              0.35      0.25     -0.14      0.82 1.00
## snh.typewoody           -0.04      0.10     -0.24      0.14 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous     -0.02      0.08     -0.18      0.15 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable      0.27      0.18     -0.07      0.61 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed        0.19      0.08      0.02      0.35 1.00
## crop.poolLegume         -0.10      0.13     -0.35      0.13 1.00
## crop.poolMaize          -0.03      0.13     -0.27      0.22 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody -0.01      0.29     -0.55      0.58 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.39      0.25     -0.87      0.09 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.28      0.45     -1.16      0.60 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed -0.01      0.21     -0.43      0.41 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.25      0.36     -0.43      0.96 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize -1.01      0.38     -1.76     -0.27 1.00
##                               Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept                   720    1044
## distance100                 2550    2600
## snh.typewoody               2756    2967
## snh.typeherbaceous          2463    2548
## crop.poolVegetable          2747    2913
## crop.poolOilseed            2838    3113
## crop.poolLegume             3047    3333
## crop.poolMaize              2997    3190
## distance100:snh.typewoody    3019    3107
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 2741    2651
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 7923    3319
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 6124    3092
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 6686    3226
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 7932    2843
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape      2.99      0.10      2.80      3.20 1.00      2107      3005
## hu          0.01      0.00      0.01      0.02 1.00      11620     2344
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Predatory

```
brm_abund_11
```

```

## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.pool
## Data: filter(meta_abund_diet, diet == "predatory") (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)          1.03      0.15      0.77      1.38 1.00      1871

```

```

## sd(distance100)          0.36      0.17      0.05      0.70 1.00      1970
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.41      0.34     -0.38      0.93 1.00      4059
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           2852
## sd(distance100)         1463
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 3762
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##                               Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           0.73      0.02      0.68      0.78 1.00      2617
## sd(distance100)         0.10      0.07      0.00      0.26 1.00      1901
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.21      0.53     -0.96      0.88 1.00      5439
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           4206
## sd(distance100)         2538
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 4762
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##                               Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept                 0.19      0.21     -0.22      0.60 1.00
## distance100                0.26      0.25     -0.25      0.74 1.00
## snh.typewoody              0.06      0.10     -0.14      0.26 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous         0.05      0.09     -0.13      0.22 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable         0.24      0.17     -0.10      0.59 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed           0.02      0.09     -0.15      0.19 1.00
## crop.poolLegume            -0.21      0.13     -0.46      0.04 1.00
## crop.poolMaize             -0.12      0.13     -0.38      0.14 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody  -0.43      0.29     -0.98      0.16 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.38      0.26     -0.86      0.13 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.06      0.47     -0.98      0.87 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed  0.09      0.24     -0.36      0.56 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume  0.14      0.38     -0.61      0.89 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize  -0.86      0.42     -1.69     -0.03 1.00
##                               Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept                 1001      1942
## distance100                3216      4957
## snh.typewoody              2635      4052
## snh.typeherbaceous         2753      4025
## crop.poolVegetable         2927      4835
## crop.poolOilseed           3147      4316
## crop.poolLegume            3510      5250
## crop.poolMaize             3550      5151
## distance100:snh.typewoody  3965      5242
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 3732      5055
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 10259      6686
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed  4724      5974
## distance100:crop.poolLegume  6981      6869
## distance100:crop.poolMaize  8716      6610
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##                               Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape                2.62      0.09      2.45      2.80 1.00      4007      5400
## hu                    0.06      0.00      0.05      0.07 1.00     12291      5689
##

```

```
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).
```

Omnivorous

```
brm_abund_12
```

```
## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.po
## Data: filter(meta_abund_diet, diet == "omnivorous") (Number of observations: 1765)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 27)
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 1.06 0.17 0.78 1.45 1.00 2047
## sd(distance100) 1.00 0.22 0.63 1.51 1.00 3375
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.30 0.24 -0.72 0.21 1.00 4190
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 3195
## sd(distance100) 5458
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 4915
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 863)
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 0.82 0.04 0.75 0.89 1.00 2293
## sd(distance100) 0.73 0.18 0.38 1.07 1.01 712
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.20 0.16 -0.46 0.15 1.00 2068
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept) 3950
## sd(distance100) 1119
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 2066
##
## Population-Level Effects:
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept -0.89 0.24 -1.36 -0.42 1.00
## distance100 0.80 0.36 0.08 1.49 1.00
## snh.typewoody -0.32 0.14 -0.60 -0.03 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous 0.03 0.12 -0.22 0.27 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable -0.04 0.37 -0.79 0.68 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed -0.07 0.12 -0.31 0.17 1.00
## crop.poolLegume 0.01 0.16 -0.31 0.32 1.00
## crop.poolMaize -0.34 0.17 -0.68 -0.00 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody 0.77 0.41 -0.04 1.56 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.24 0.35 -0.93 0.46 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 0.12 0.70 -1.24 1.49 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 0.31 0.35 -0.37 0.98 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.35 0.45 -0.51 1.24 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize -0.53 0.55 -1.60 0.53 1.00
## Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept 1292 2515
```

```

## distance100                4075    5046
## snh.typewoody              3466    5102
## snh.typeherbaceous         3073    5043
## crop.poolVegetable         6437    6255
## crop.poolOilseed           3766    5181
## crop.poolLegume            4173    5219
## crop.poolMaize             3855    5045
## distance100:snh.typewoody   5913    6334
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 4812    5559
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 14245    6376
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed  5653    5595
## distance100:crop.poolLegume   6311    5876
## distance100:crop.poolMaize    8146    6303
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape      2.27      0.11   2.07   2.49 1.00     2240     4757
## hu         0.05      0.01   0.04   0.06 1.00    15112     5482
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Omnivorous (without *Poecilus cupreus*)

```
brm_abund_12b
```

```

## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.pool
## Data: filter(meta_abund_diet_b, diet == "omnivorous") (Number of observations: 213)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
##      total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 21)
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.81    0.17   0.53   1.22 1.00     2145
## sd(distance100)    0.38    0.27   0.02   1.02 1.00     2811
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.30    0.50  -0.78   0.97 1.00     5145
##      Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      3720
## sd(distance100)    2706
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 4725
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 150)
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.48    0.07   0.35   0.61 1.00     2615
## sd(distance100)    0.30    0.23   0.01   0.88 1.00     1901
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.25    0.52  -0.96   0.87 1.00     4828
##      Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      4678
## sd(distance100)    2411
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 4703

```

```

##
## Population-Level Effects:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept          -2.79      0.28   -3.32   -2.24 1.00
## distance100          0.25      0.44   -0.58    1.13 1.00
## snh.typewoody        -0.14      0.26   -0.65    0.38 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous   -0.26      0.20   -0.65    0.14 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable    0.00      0.40   -0.76    0.78 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed     -0.18      0.25   -0.65    0.30 1.00
## crop.poolLegume      -0.04      0.31   -0.65    0.58 1.00
## crop.poolMaize        0.22      0.29   -0.34    0.77 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody  0.04      0.56   -1.08    1.13 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.44      0.45   -1.35    0.43 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.38      0.71   -1.76    1.02 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed  0.01      0.53   -1.04    1.03 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume  -0.03      0.69   -1.38    1.33 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize   0.16      0.66   -1.13    1.44 1.00
##           Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept          2145    4061
## distance100          4451    5027
## snh.typewoody        4612    5563
## snh.typeherbaceous   4237    5499
## crop.poolVegetable   4370    5479
## crop.poolOilseed     4232    5199
## crop.poolLegume      5641    5888
## crop.poolMaize       5199    5573
## distance100:snh.typewoody  5748    5673
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 4732    5355
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 9707    6277
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed  6509    6118
## distance100:crop.poolLegume  9174    6299
## distance100:crop.poolMaize   7386    6051
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape      3.02      0.38    2.32    3.81 1.00    2978    5148
## hu          0.00      0.00    0.00    0.02 1.00    7269    4134
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Granivorous

```
brm_abund_20
```

```

## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.po
## Data: filter(meta_abund_diet, diet == "granivorous") (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 2000; warmup = 1000; thin = 1;
##           total post-warmup draws = 4000
##
## Group-Level Effects:

```

```

## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           0.57    0.10    0.41    0.79 1.00    1392
## sd(distance100)          0.13    0.12    0.01    0.44 1.00    1756
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.10    0.49   -0.92    0.88 1.00    5210
##           Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           2051
## sd(distance100)          2413
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 3209
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           0.74    0.03    0.69    0.79 1.00    1546
## sd(distance100)          0.15    0.10    0.01    0.37 1.00     730
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.34    0.45   -0.75    0.97 1.00    3153
##           Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           2489
## sd(distance100)          1194
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 2499
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept           -1.26    0.14   -1.54   -0.97 1.00
## distance100          -0.71    0.24   -1.17   -0.25 1.00
## snh.typewoody        -0.31    0.11   -0.53   -0.09 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous  -0.32    0.09   -0.50   -0.14 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable   0.47    0.20    0.08    0.84 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed     1.01    0.09    0.83    1.18 1.00
## crop.poolLegume       0.01    0.13   -0.26    0.27 1.00
## crop.poolMaize        0.35    0.14    0.07    0.62 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody 0.24    0.29   -0.34    0.82 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 0.34    0.25   -0.15    0.81 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.68    0.51   -1.66    0.31 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 0.16    0.22   -0.28    0.60 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.35    0.38   -0.37    1.09 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize -0.45    0.47   -1.37    0.44 1.00
##           Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept           1317    1561
## distance100          3147    3036
## snh.typewoody        2529    2809
## snh.typeherbaceous  2249    2572
## crop.poolVegetable   2904    2933
## crop.poolOilseed     2291    2952
## crop.poolLegume       2920    3245
## crop.poolMaize        2711    2825
## distance100:snh.typewoody 3765    3192
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 3351    3057
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 7225    2849
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 5367    2868
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 5369    3449
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 6450    3367
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS

```

```
## shape      2.79      0.11      2.58      3.02 1.00      1843      2520
## hu         0.27      0.01      0.25      0.28 1.00      9700      2459
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).
```

Small

```
brm_abund_30
```

```
## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.pool
## Data: filter(meta_abund_size, size.class == "small") (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 2000; warmup = 1000; thin = 1;
## total post-warmup draws = 4000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.71      0.12      0.52      0.97 1.00      1653
## sd(distance100)    0.53      0.20      0.16      0.96 1.00      1163
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.28      0.29      -0.32      0.80 1.00      2238
##
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      2386
## sd(distance100)    988
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 1410
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.72      0.03      0.67      0.78 1.00      1683
## sd(distance100)    0.16      0.12      0.01      0.43 1.00      642
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.16      0.48      -0.85      0.95 1.00      3419
##
## Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      2815
## sd(distance100)    1092
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 2153
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##
## Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept          -1.35      0.17      -1.67      -1.01 1.00
## distance100         -0.28      0.30      -0.90      0.28 1.00
## snh.typewoody       0.19      0.12      -0.03      0.42 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous 0.01      0.10      -0.18      0.20 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable 0.67      0.19      0.30      1.04 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed   0.11      0.10      -0.09      0.30 1.00
## crop.poolLegume    -0.06      0.15      -0.36      0.25 1.00
## crop.poolMaize     0.19      0.14      -0.09      0.47 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody -0.14      0.34      -0.81      0.52 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.08      0.29      -0.65      0.52 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.08      0.51      -1.06      0.94 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 0.26      0.29      -0.31      0.83 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.07      0.46      -0.81      0.96 1.00
```

```

## distance100:crop.poolMaize      -1.04      0.46    -1.93    -0.13  1.00
##                               Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept                       1179      2014
## distance100                     2496      2516
## snh.typewoody                   2248      2915
## snh.typeherbaceous              2149      2424
## crop.poolVegetable              2668      2903
## crop.poolOilseed                2351      2790
## crop.poolLegume                 2546      2661
## crop.poolMaize                  2746      2903
## distance100:snh.typewoody       3786      3425
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous  3356      2824
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable  6229      3289
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed    2739      2232
## distance100:crop.poolLegume     5064      3364
## distance100:crop.poolMaize     6328      2923
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape      2.55      0.10    2.36    2.76 1.00    2051    2936
## hu          0.28      0.01    0.27    0.30 1.00    9493    2804
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Medium

```
brm_abund_40
```

```

## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.pool
## Data: filter(meta_abund_size, size.class == "medium") (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 4000; warmup = 2000; thin = 1;
##      total post-warmup draws = 8000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      1.00      0.15    0.75    1.34 1.00    1151
## sd(distance100)    0.24      0.15    0.01    0.59 1.00    1604
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.27      0.43   -0.69    0.94 1.00    4104
##                               Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      2042
## sd(distance100)    2719
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 3570
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)      0.67      0.02    0.63    0.72 1.00    2021
## sd(distance100)    0.11      0.08    0.00    0.31 1.00    1063
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 0.24      0.49   -0.84    0.96 1.00    4301
##                               Tail_ESS

```

```

## sd(Intercept)          3907
## sd(distance100)       1529
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 3866
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept          -0.34    0.21  -0.74    0.06  1.00
## distance100         -0.16    0.24  -0.64    0.29  1.00
## snh.typewoody       -0.18    0.10  -0.38    0.02  1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous  -0.04    0.09  -0.20    0.13  1.00
## crop.poolVegetable -0.15    0.21  -0.56    0.26  1.00
## crop.poolOilseed    0.55    0.08   0.38    0.72  1.00
## crop.poolLegume     -0.14    0.13  -0.40    0.12  1.00
## crop.poolMaize      -0.62    0.13  -0.88   -0.36  1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody 0.36    0.30  -0.20    0.96  1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.16    0.25  -0.64    0.33  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.44    0.54  -1.49    0.62  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed -0.01    0.22  -0.44    0.44  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume -0.48    0.39  -1.24    0.27  1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 0.09    0.47  -0.81    1.02  1.00
##
##           Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept           797   1405
## distance100        3061   4080
## snh.typewoody       1921   3375
## snh.typeherbaceous  1986   3197
## crop.poolVegetable  2938   4670
## crop.poolOilseed    2714   4425
## crop.poolLegume     2910   4497
## crop.poolMaize      2745   4844
## distance100:snh.typewoody 2950   4859
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 3534   4600
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 7027   5861
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 4341   5124
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 4820   5905
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 7858   6056
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape      2.93    0.11   2.72   3.15  1.00   2923   5061
## hu          0.18    0.01   0.17   0.20  1.00   9039   6079
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```

Large

```
brm_abund_50
```

```

## Family: hurdle_gamma
## Links: mu = log; shape = identity; hu = identity
## Formula: abund.std ~ distance100 + snh.type + crop.pool + distance100:snh.type + distance100:crop.pool
## Data: filter(meta_abund_size, size.class == "large") (Number of observations: 2768)
## Draws: 4 chains, each with iter = 5000; warmup = 2500; thin = 1;

```

```

##           total post-warmup draws = 10000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~study (Number of levels: 28)
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           1.02    0.16    0.77    1.37 1.00    1961
## sd(distance100)          0.87    0.17    0.57    1.25 1.00    3566
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.07    0.24   -0.52    0.40 1.00    3757
##           Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           3892
## sd(distance100)          5548
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 5388
##
## ~study:site (Number of levels: 1204)
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           0.83    0.03    0.77    0.88 1.00    1651
## sd(distance100)          0.54    0.19    0.08    0.87 1.00    486
## cor(Intercept,distance100) -0.26    0.20   -0.57    0.21 1.00    2906
##           Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)           4428
## sd(distance100)          527
## cor(Intercept,distance100) 1338
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##           Estimate Est.Error l-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat
## Intercept              -0.12    0.22   -0.54    0.31 1.00
## distance100              0.75    0.30    0.15    1.34 1.00
## snh.typewoody            -0.12    0.11   -0.33    0.10 1.00
## snh.typeherbaceous       -0.06    0.10   -0.25    0.13 1.00
## crop.poolVegetable        0.17    0.19   -0.20    0.56 1.00
## crop.poolOilseed         -0.04    0.10   -0.23    0.15 1.00
## crop.poolLegume          -0.07    0.14   -0.34    0.20 1.00
## crop.poolMaize            0.04    0.14   -0.24    0.32 1.00
## distance100:snh.typewoody -0.13    0.33   -0.77    0.53 1.00
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous -0.47    0.29   -1.01    0.09 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable -0.41    0.53   -1.43    0.61 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 0.20    0.27   -0.32    0.75 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 0.31    0.38   -0.43    1.05 1.00
## distance100:crop.poolMaize -0.79    0.45   -1.67    0.09 1.00
##           Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept                980    1997
## distance100              3479    5935
## snh.typewoody            2586    4662
## snh.typeherbaceous       2266    4257
## crop.poolVegetable        3135    4814
## crop.poolOilseed         2828    5142
## crop.poolLegume          3043    4647
## crop.poolMaize            2915    5102
## distance100:snh.typewoody 4884    6712
## distance100:snh.typeherbaceous 4222    6227
## distance100:crop.poolVegetable 9960    7583
## distance100:crop.poolOilseed 5425    6577
## distance100:crop.poolLegume 6265    7011
## distance100:crop.poolMaize 9281    7501

```

```
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##      Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## shape      2.50      0.10    2.32    2.69 1.00     1665     3553
## hu         0.07      0.00    0.06    0.08 1.00    12665     7201
##
## Draws were sampled using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).
```

Evaluate empirical realism via posterior predictive checking

In a posterior predictive check, we simulate data by sampling from the posterior of a model. This expresses what the model “expects” to see in a new set of empirical data. The logic is similar to that of a prior-predictive check, except now our model has learned from the data. If the data-generating process has been captured reasonably by the model, data predicted from the posterior should be distributed similarly to the data used to fit the model (or, better yet, to a real new data set—but this is not usually available). We visualize the posterior predictive check by plotting draws from the posterior (light blue) over the distribution of the data used to fit the model (dark blue). Systematic deviations between the real and simulated data indicate that the model is not doing a good job of representing the real-world data-generating process.

Richness

Total

```
pp_check(brm_rich_00)
```


Predatory

```
pp_check(brm_rich_11)
```


Omnivorous

```
pp_check(brm_rich_12)
```


Omnivorous (without *P. cupreus*)

```
pp_check(brm_rich_12b)
```


Granivorous

```
pp_check(brm_rich_20)
```


Activity density

Total

```
pp_check(brm_abund_00)
```


Predatory

```
pp_check(brm_abund_11)
```


Omnivorous

```
pp_check(brm_abund_12)
```


Omnivorous (without *P. cupreus*)

```
pp_check(brm_abund_12b)
```


Granivorous

```
pp_check(brm_abund_20)
```


Small

```
pp_check(brm_abund_30)
```


Medium

```
pp_check(brm_abund_40)
```


Large

```
pp_check(brm_abund_50)
```


-> ->

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